

Supplementary figures to:

Georgieva MN, Taboada S, Riesgo A, Díez-Vives C, De Leo FC, Jeffreys RM, Copley JT, Little CTS, Ríos P, Cristobo J, Hestetun JT and Glover AG (2020) Evidence of vent-adaptation in sponges living at the periphery of hydrothermal vent environments: ecological and evolutionary implications. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 11:1636. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2020.01636

Figure S1. Relative abundances (log10 transformed) of the most common prokaryotes for individual sponge samples at the genus level. Genera with relative abundances lower than 0.5% across the dataset were omitted from the figure. The heatmaps also illustrate similarity (weighted UniFrac distance cladograms) of microbiome composition for each microbiome dataset analysed, **A**, *Cladorhiza-Chondrocladia* (Dataset 1) and **B**, *Spinularia-Sycon* (Dataset 2), while **C**, Cladorhizidae dataset generated by Hestetun et al. (2016) (Dataset 3). Genus and species names are abbreviated as follows: Cl. *Cladorhiza*, Ch. *Chondrocladia*, rob. *robertballardi*, ver. *verticillata*, Ly. cup. *Lycopina cupressiformis*, As. *Asbestopluma*, meth. *methanophila*, abyss. *abyssicola*, cort. *corticocancellata*, Spi. *Spinularia*, Sy. *Sycon*.

Figure S2. Carbon and nitrogen isotopic results ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) for E2 *Cladorhiza* and Endeavour *Spinularia* sp. specimens analysed during the present study in comparison to results for cladorhizid sponges from the previous studies of Erickson et al., (2009), Reid et al. (2013), Hestetun et al. (2016).

References

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